

Early-Stage Autism Spectrum Disorder Detection With Convolutional Neural Network Model

Asif.K.A.
PG Scholar

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirapally,India
asifka9116@gmail.com

Meera Rose Mathew
Assistant Professor

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirapally,India
meerarosemathew@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Autism is a developmental condition that impacts youngsters and worsens with age. A youngster with autism has trouble interacting with people and communicating, as well as having limited behaviour, but with proper care and therapy. Autistic children who are diagnosed early have a higher chance of having a normal life. So, they can have a quality life. However, in many cases, Children who have autism are diagnosed lately. Moreover, there are no particular medical tests for autism. It must be diagnosed by a qualified medical professional. Medical personnel take a significantly large amount of time to detect it because the children must be properly monitored and observed. In this paper, we use ML algorithm for detecting autism in children from facial images of children that are not viable for ordinary people. Here we are using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to categorize children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Using Image Processing, we were able to reach the maximum accuracy of 74.33 percent on CNN with image dataset. The results of the assessment revealed that the suggested prediction model performs better for datasets in terms of accuracy, specificity, sensitivity and precision

Keywords—Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), Machine Learning (ML), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

I. INTRODUCTION

Autism is caused due to imperfect development of brain during birth which affects their social and personal life. The main concern with this condition is that it causes children to be unable to grasp, learn appropriately, engage, and communicate. Autism may be recognised in children as well as adults. Autism affects one out of every fifty-four children, according to studies. Autism affects people of different ages and backgrounds. It doesn't matter where you're from. Boys are four times more likely than females to be diagnosed with autism. Autism is most usually discovered after the age of four, however it can sometimes be discovered around the age of two. The sooner they're discovered, the easier it will be to deal with them. It is possible to enhance autistic children's behaviour and communicative skills if they receive sufficient care and treatment. Doctors, psychologists, and experts now assess children's behaviour and growth to identify whether they are autistic or not, which takes time and needs highly experienced professionals. Identifying autistic youngsters just by monitoring their behavioural actions over time is a difficult task for doctors or physicians. Also, there is a shortage of medical specialists in many remote and

underdeveloped areas. People living in these places are unable to afford medical care. As a result, most family members are unaware to find their children has autism. This causes the autistic children to grows up without sufficient care, therapy, or treatment. Many researchers are now working on computer-assisted decision-making systems that employ machine learning to identify autism in youngsters.

To deal with such problems. They gathered information regarding children's behaviour using a range of interviews and questionnaires. To identify ASD early on, many prediction models based on machine learning technology might be applied. A face dataset has never been used to diagnose autism in children. Almost everyone has used text and numerical data in interviews and surveys, which are time-consuming and error prone. As a result of these outdated procedures, children under the age of eight may become afraid during interviews and surveys. As a consequence of their lack of information on numerous issues, children may get concerned and give incorrect replies. The prediction model will be skewed as a result of these inaccurate replies, diminishing forecast accuracy. To address these concerns, we created a basic prediction model based on the faces of 2940 children ranging in age from 2 to 8. We used the CNN Algorithm to classify ASD from an image collection of autistic youngsters in this study. Face photos of 2940 youngsters are included in the collection. We utilize CNN to classify ASD in children once we finish the picture processing stage.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The current way for diagnosing ASD is to examine the person's features. The most important problem with this approach of diagnosing ASD is that it can be deceptive when distinguishing it from other diseases. In order to distinguish ASD from other neurodevelopmental problems (DDs). Bone Omar [1] developed a smartphone app that can detect ASD in people of any age. In this work, the random forest technique's Iterative Dichotomiser3 (ID3) and Classification and Regression Trees (CART) were utilized to develop a machine learning model. When Ozturk [4] looked at the performance of RF, Radial Basis Function Network (RBFN), Naive Bayes, and K- Nearest Neighbors (KNN) for detecting ASD in children, they found that RF, Radial Basis Function Network (RBFN), Naive Bayes, and K- Nearest Neighbors

(KNN) performed the best. They gathered Autistic Spectrum Disorder Screening Data from the UCI machine learning repository for their study. RF beat the other classifying algorithms, according to their findings. KNN and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) were used by Altay [5] to diagnose ASD in children aged 4 to 11. They adopted a 70:30 split for training and testing. These effective for getting prediction accuracy while lowering prediction bias. In the Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange (ABIDE) dataset, Heinsfeld [2] employed deep learning algorithms to categorize ASD. They were able to achieve a classification accuracy of 70%, which was greater than other cutting-edge methods.

III. DATASET DESCRIPTION

This study used a facial image dataset of autistic children from the Kaggle library. There are 2940 images of children's faces in this collection, evenly split across autistic and non-autistic classes. The majority of the photographs in this collection are of children between the ages of 2 and 8. The male-to-female ratio in the autistic class is 3:1, while it is 1:1 in the non-autistic class. Figure 1 shows several examples of facial images from this dataset.

Figure.1. Samples of Face Images

(a) Autistic Children

(b) Non-Autistic Children

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Image Preprocessing

All of the images in this dataset were of various sizes. In order to convert all the images in to similar size ,we used the resize function from Python OpenCV. After that we performed color space conversion . All of the photos were converted to the BGR colour space, which specifies a load of colour space. The image processing was finalized by transforming all of the pictures into an array that could be

used in later operations. Illustrates the flow diagram for our paper.

Figure. 2. Workflow of Our Research Methodology

B. Classification

Convolutional Neural network (CNN)

CNN, is a part of a deep neural network most commonly developed for classifying computer vision tasks. A CNN architecture is completed through the convolutional layer's connection, pooling layer, and fully connected layer. In the convolutional layer, a feature detector or kernel helps extract features from the input image and creates a convolved image. Mathematically, the following equation represents the convolutional operation:

$$(f * g)(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(T) g(t - T) dT \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

ReLU adds non-linearity to the network after finishing the convolution procedure. The following list consists of the function's output:

$$f(x) = \max(0, x) \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

To create a pooled feature map, features are taken from the convolved picture in the pooling layer. The artificial neural network is then given this pooled feature map as an input. An input layer, numerous hidden layers, and an output layer make up the fully - connected layer. The output layer delivers the final prediction, and all nodes in the completely connected levels are fully linked.

C. EVALUATION MEASURES

For the evaluation of classification algorithm's performance, we employed five assessment measures: accuracy, ROC AUC, F-1 score, precision, and recall. The following formulae can be used to calculate all of these assessment metrics:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TN+TP}{TN+TP+FN+FP} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{FP+TP} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{FN+TP} \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

$$F1 - Score = \frac{2TP}{FN+FP+2TP} \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

The terms of those above equations represent,

- TN = True Negative
- TP = True Positive
- FP = False Positive
- FN = False Negative

The ROC AUC is a visual representation that illustrates the efficiency of a binary classification system.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Jupyter, a cloud-based environment, and Python-3 as a programming language were employed in this paper. In Jupyter we utilized the Virtual Tensor Processing Unit (TPU) to enhance the execution of classification algorithms. Following the data pre-processing stage, the entire dataset is divided into an 8:2 ratio, with 80% utilized for training and 20% preserved for testing.

In this paper, We separated autistic and non-autistic children from a dataset of autistic children using CNN classification methods. When we looked at the accuracy of the experimental outcomes, we observed that CNN was 74% accurate. When looking into the ROC AUC value, it's determined that CNN has a ROC AUC of 74%. The CNN classifier has produced the same findings as before when looking at the F1-score and precision values, with F1-score and precision values of 75% and 74%, respectively. Figure 3 shows ROC AUC Graph

Figure 3

CNN also holds the recall value of 74, Based on the results of the preceding experiment Check the prognosis of the disease for the available input dataset. Based on the level of accuracy, the disease with the highest accuracy predetermined will be finalized as disease.

Based on the model, the CNN will predict the children who autistic or not. The result is shown in fig 4. The output image will show if the kid is autistic or not.

Figure 4

We may conclude that CNN outperformed all other assessment criteria in identifying autistic children using facial images.

VI. DISCUSSION

Our proposed CNN architecture is briefly described in this section. In terms of classification performance for predicting ASD in image datasets, the CNN method has already beaten other machine learning algorithms. Figures 4.1 and 4.2 show the structure of our proposed VGG16 Model and CNN Model.

Figure 4.1 Structure of VGG16 Model

Figure 4.2 Structure of CNN Model

The images in the dataset had different sizes. So, they were reformatted into 64x64. Each of the first two convolution layers extracts features from input images, for a total of 64 filters of 3x3 sizes. VGG16 contains 16 layers and it is used as the base layer. After that, we can use a Flatten layer to reduce the input's spatial dimensions into the channel dimension, and ReLU was chosen as the activation function with shape 512. Then, at each step during the training period, we utilize the Dropout layer, which sets input units to 0 at random with a rated frequency. Then we apply a layer with sigmoid activation.

To prevent the model from overfitting, dropout layers were added between the hidden layers. Because the ASD screening was a simple binary categorization. In the last layer, the activation function was Sigmoid. Adam served as the optimizer, and binary-cross entropy served as the loss function. The proposed CNN model was trained and tested for 60 epochs, with a batch size (hyperparameter of gradient descent) of 16 selected to increase robustness and decrease overfitting-underfitting concerns.

After each epoch, the loss value gradually decreases and the accuracy improves. After 60 epochs of testing, the suggested CNN model had a testing accuracy of 74.33 percent in diagnosing autistic youngsters. The overall training and testing performances of the proposed CNN model for diagnosing autistic children from face photos are given and contrasted. Figure 5 depicts the categorization report.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.70	0.84	0.77	150
1	0.80	0.65	0.72	150
accuracy			0.74	300
macro avg	0.75	0.74	0.74	300
weighted avg	0.75	0.74	0.74	300

Fig 5 Classification Report

VII. CONCLUSION

ASD is very difficult to diagnose because there is no appropriate medical test, such as a blood test, scanning etc. In order to do, doctors examine the child's developmental history and behaviour. According to experts, no one can tell if a child is autistic simply by looking at them. As a result, before concluding, medical specialists go through a series of processes to study children's behaviour and activities. Artificial intelligence (AI) is crucial for resolving this problem since it allows us to classify images of autistic children into two categories: autistic and non-autistic. It is not possible for people to simply determine autism in children by looking at their images. Artificial intelligence can be used to determine it since it can locate and classify photos with delicate and detailed properties. In this study, CNN was used to diagnose autism in children without the help of a doctor or other medical expert. As a result, it can use this prediction model as an alternative to traditional methods. In addition, they may accurately detect autism in toddlers in a short period. A total of 2940 toddler images were used in this investigation. Our prediction model will become stronger and can be identified more correctly as the number of images increases. This model can be deployed into the cloud which allows medical professionals to use this model more quickly in diagnosing a new child.

VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] Kazi Shahrukh Omar; Prodipta Mondal; Nabila Shahnaz Khan; Md. Rezaul Karim Rizvi; Md Nazrul Islam, A Machine Learning Approach to Predict Autism Spectrum Disorder | IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE XploreS.
- [2] Heinsfeld, A. R. Franco, R. C. Craddock, A. Buchweitz and F. Meneguzzi, Identification of autism spectrum disorder using deep learning and the ABIDE dataset - PMC (nih.gov)
- [3] J. Yuan, C. Holtz, T. Smith and J. Luo, Autism spectrum disorder detection from semi-structured and unstructured medical data - PubMed (nih.gov)
- [4] F. N. Büyükoğuz and A. Ozturk, Early autism diagnosis of children with machine learning algorithms | IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore
- [5] Itay and M. Ulas, Prediction of the autism spectrum disorder diagnosis with linear discriminant analysis classifier and K-nearest neighbour in children | IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore
- [6] Autistic Children Data Set, Autism_Image_Data | Kaggle